

DEVELOPMENT OF POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES REINFORCED BY CARBON NANOTUBES WITH 3-D NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

With unique structure and transport properties, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted much interest in developing polymer nanocomposites with exceptional mechanical and multi-functional characteristics. However, if these nanofillers are to be utilized as effective reinforcements in polymer composites, proper dispersion and good interfacial bonding between the filler and polymer matrix have to be guaranteed. Therefore, many different surface treatment and functionalization processes were employed to improve the dispersion and interfacial adhesion of CNTs with polymer resins. One of the major disadvantages of utilizing these techniques is that they can cut CNTs into pieces and create many surface defects on CNT sidewalls, resulting in the decreased aspect ratios of nanomaterials and severe degradation on their mechanical and transport properties.

The objective of this work is to employ carbon-based nanofillers with new morphologies, i.e., interconnected CNT foam (CF), as functional reinforcement for polymer nanocomposites. The foams with 3-D structures can absorb a variety of polymers by more than 50 times of their own weight with stabilized networks, ultimately eliminating the problems associated with the dispersion and agglomeration of CNTs in polymers. The effect of CF on the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) will be presented. The application of these nanocomposites as sensors to monitor the motions like finger bending, breathing, will also be presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted much attention in preparing polymer nanocomposites due to their unique structures and excellent mechanical and electrical properties [1]. Proper dispersion and good interfacial interactions between CNTs and polymer matrix are two key issues to prepare CNT/polymer nanocomposites with enhanced properties. Utilization of CNTs with different forms [2-4], like the powder, film, assembly on the surface of carbon fiber, have been developed as reinforcements for polymers.

Recent progress made on the preparation of carbon-based foam has achieved much interest due to the tunable properties and high porosity in the foam structure. Various methods, like dip coating, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), have been reported to prepare 3-D foam consisting of novel carbon-based nanoparticles (CNTs or graphene). For the first method, Yu [5] made graphene-polyurethane sponge by combination of dip coating and hydrothermal treatment. Cui [6] obtained CNT sponge by coating a polymer sponge in CNT dispersion. CVD method is widely used for the fabrication of CNT foam. For example, Eom [7] prepared CNT arrays on silicon wafer via CVD and the mechanical properties of CNT array were studied using atomic force microscope. Zhang [8] controlled the parameters of CVD process to change the morphology and spinnability of CNT arrays. Some other researches focused on the controlling of processing parameters to modulate the properties of CNT arrays [9, 10]. Worsley [11] used carbon nanoparticles to enhance the mechanical properties of the CNT foam.

Reddy [12] used fluid which is response to magnetic field to tailor the mechanical properties of corresponding foam.

In addition, unaligned carbon foam took more attention due to easier procedure to prepare and higher scalability to be fabricated in large quantity, as reported by various groups on the preparation of CNT or graphene foam using Ni foam as template in CVD chamber [13-15]. One of the major problems for CVD method is that the metal template should be removed using acid before the foam can be incorporated into polymer matrix, and this process will lead the damages to the structure and properties of CNT or graphene. In addition, the high cost arising from the metal foam impact the practical application of foam materials. To overcome this problem, Wu used a modified CVD method by the continuously injection of catalysts into the chamber to prepare CNT sponge [16]. While the method is novel, few studies were reported in this field to prepare CNT foam without metal template.

This paper reported the preparation of CNT foam using melamine-formaldehyde foam (MF) as a template. The novelty of this study lies in the fact that polymer template was much cheaper than metal, and can be thermally decomposed under high temperature, making the final foam contain CNT only. The properties of CNT/polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) were studied and reported.

2. EXPERIMENTAL:

2.1 Preparation of CF

1mmol/L of Fe^{3+} solution was prepared by dissolving $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ into water, and MF was immersed into the solution for 30 min. The foam was collected and compressed to remove water inside and then dried in an oven for 2h, yielding Fe^{3+} deposited foam. The foam was put into the tube furnace of CVD system, then heated to 800 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The sample as kept at this temperature for 0.5 h under Ar/ H_2 (20:1 by volume), this was followed by the introduction of C_2H_2 into the system for 0.5h. After that, the furnace was cooled to room temperature in Ar atmosphere, producing CF sample for characterization and application.

2.2 Preparation of CF/PDMS

In order to make CNT foam/PDMS, we put CNT foam in the liquid of PDMS (Dow Corning Sylgard 184, mixture of a monomer and curing agent with volume ratio of 10:1), resulting in the infusion of PDMS into CF via the capillary forces. After 40 min, CF was suspended in PDMS, suggesting the fully penetration of PDMS into foam. Then the sample was put into the oven at 100 °C for 1 h. The resultant solids were trimmed until the surfaces of CNT foam were exposed for the measurement of electrical conductivity. The cured samples were named as CF/PDMS.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Supra55VP, Germany) was used to characterize the morphology of related samples. The electrical properties were measured by digital multimeter (Agilent 34410A). Mechanical test for the samples was performed on a universal testing machine (UTM, C43.104, MTS). The piezoresistance effect (under compression and tension) of samples was performed by combination of the electrical resistance measurement and tensile test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Morphology and electrical properties of CF

Figure 1a showed the photographs of MF, Fe^{3+} deposited MF (Fe^{3+} -MF) and CF. From the Fig. 1, we find that the color is different among these three samples: Fe^{3+} -MF turned into yellow because of the deposition of Fe^{3+} and CF was black due to carbonization in high temperature (Fig. 1a). The morphology of sample exhibited obvious difference according to the SEM results (b and c in Fig. 1): MF has the smooth skeleton while CF is surrounded completely by CNTs with length of about 10~20um, which indicated the successful preparation of CF. In addition, CF also inherited the 3D interconnected network with the

smaller pore size of 100~200 μm from MF and thus, CF hold the density of $22.43 \pm 6.33 \text{ mg/cm}^3$ and porosity of 94.3%. CNTs on the skeleton of foam were twisted and wrapped on the skeleton in a random distribution unlike an aligned styles [7], such as forest and array. The incorporation of CNTs in the foam endows the whole materials electrically conductive, the measured electrical conductivity of CF is below $\sim 10^{-4} \text{ S/cm}$, which is much higher than that of MF ($<10^{-13} \text{ S/cm}$).

Fig. 1 The morphology of samples and SEM images.

3.2 Absorption behavior of CF to organic liquids

Fig. 2 Oil absorption capacity of CF

The porous structure of foam makes it possible for the material to adsorb organic liquids. In order to evaluate the absorption capacity of CF, several chemicals or oily compounds were employed as probing liquids to evaluate the adsorption capacity of CF, as shown in Fig. 2. In general, the adsorption capacity of CF for various liquid materials is in the range of 30~80 times, depending on the density of organics. In addition, considering hydrophobicity of CF due to the presence of CNTs and high temperature treatment, CF is a very promising material in the application of oil-water separation. The high adsorption capacity for liquid polymer/monomer, for example, the CF can retain more than 40 times of its own weight for epoxy monomer, makes the foam can be a filler for polymer reinforcement.

3.3 Piezoresistivity of CF-PDMS composites

3.3.1 Compression test

Fig. 3 Morphology and piezoresistive performance of CF-PDMS composites (a: SEM image shows the fractured surface of CF-PDMS composites; b: Load-strain curve of CF-PDMS under the compression; c: Resistance change - strain curve of sample; d: Resistance change of CF-PDMS under the cyclic compression)

Given the 3D interconnected network of CF, we explored its application as sensor for mechanical forces. Commonly, the ideal sensor should be conductive, stretchable or flexible. Therefore, although it has a high electrical conductivity, CF is fragile as it cannot be recovered and be destroyed severely under the mechanical loads, which made it not suitable for strain sensor alone. A common strategy is to incorporate another soft matrix [17]. Here we used PDMS to penetrate into the pores of CF to modulate the mechanical properties of materials under the mechanical conditions. Fig. 3a showed the fractured surface of CNT-PDMS, and the result showed that PDMS filled most of the empty space in CF, including the holes made by carbonized skeletons and the gaps between CNTs in skeleton.

To evaluate the piezoresistivity of CFPS, the electrical resistance between top and bottom surfaces was recorded simultaneously with loading and unloading compression applied between these two surfaces. The load-unload strain curve was a hysteresis loop, which originated from the viscoelastic behavior of PDMS and the excellent recovery capability (Fig. 3b). Fig. 3c shows the corresponding piezoresistive properties and two regions can be divided at $\sim 5\%$ of compression strain. In the first region (0~5%), the electrical resistance declined with increasing compression. In the second region (5~7.7%), the resistance remained constant. This decrease on electrical resistance below 5% is possibly caused by the declined distance and more contacts between the carbonized skeletons and between CNTs, which dominated the resistance of conductive networks, and the platform in 5~7.7% suggests the saturation of such trend under the extremely mechanical condition, and the piezoresistive behavior of composites coincided quietly with that of compression without hysteresis in this region. The sensitivity of material to mechanical load can be represented by gauge factor (GF), described by the following equations:

$$GF = \frac{R(\varepsilon) - R_0}{R_0} / \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

The GF of composites in the strain below 5% is about 10, suggesting the high sensitivity of materials to mechanical forces. For further investigation on the stability, we performed cyclic test of 100 cycles at the peak strain of 5% (Elastic region). For simplicity, here we displayed the first 10 cycles and the last 10 cycles (Fig. 3d). The results showed that the resistance change of CF-PDMS under the cyclic compression is stable under the whole operations, and the lowest limitation has almost no change while an increase tendency of starting value at the beginning of every cycle was observed in every cycle number.

3.3.2 Tensile test

Fig. 4 a) Piezoresistive property of CF-PDMS with tensile strain of 33% and 55%.
(b) Cycle test of CFPS in tensile strain of 50%.

Other than performance under compression, we further measured their properties when suffered extension. Fig. 4a shows the results at the extension ratio of 33% and 50%. The result showed that the resistance of sample increased with tension and the comparison between maximum tension ratio of 33% and 50% showed more extension created more resistance change, the resistance value would monotonously increase without the platform like under the compression condition, which is possibly due to the distance between CNTs and between skeletons increased under tension. GF under tension is ~ 5 at 50% extension ratio according to the equation (2). The above results show the sample could display the electromechanical properties even in large tension, which could be employed for various sensory applications. Other strain sensor like graphene/PDMS [13] had a much lower gauge factor of 1, and the sensor based on silver nanofibres-elastomer [18] has the comparable properties as our work. In addition, the recovery is also excellent as the resistance of sample could go back during the unloading process. To investigate the stability in dynamic state, we performed cyclic test in tension strain peak of 50%. The results show that the electrical resistance of sample kept stable and displayed a negligible change in tension and corresponding releasing state over 100 cycles (Fig. 4b). The good electromechanical stability shows that the CF/PDMS has the great potential as stretchable sensors.

3.4 The application of CF-PDMS as finger motion detector

Since CFPS is large stretchable, flexible, sensitive, reliable and easily shaped, it can be used for a wearable electronic device to detect the motions from human body. We measured the electromechanical performance of CF-PDMS to display the potential uses in the field of wearable electronics. A CF-PDMS ($5 \times 1 \times 0.3$ cm) was mounted onto the glove (Fig. 5a) acting as an artificial finger so that the sensor could be in extension state when bending. The copper wires connected the ends of CF-PDMS with a digital multi-meter. We recorded the resistance

change of bending and release motions of the finger which were tried to keep the same for different cycles. The results were shown in Fig. 5b and it can be observed that the resistance increased in bending process and decreased in releasing process, and the resistance change ratio reached 10%, which is dependent on bending state. Furthermore, the resistance change is synchronous with finger motion without hysteresis, showing the rapid response time of material. More importantly, the change range showed rather stable among the bending-releasing cycles, indicating the potential applications of CF-PDMS for wearable electronics.

Figure: 5 (a) CFPS used for finger motion detection. (b) Response of sensor when the finger turned from bending and relaxation.

CONCLUSION

CF was prepared from melamine-formaldehyde sponge via CVD and it displayed large potential in various applications. CF could adsorb a variety of polymers and organics by 30~80 times of their own weight due to its high porosity and oleophilic properties arising from the inherent nature of C-based materials as well as high temperature treatment. The interconnected 3-D structures and high conductivity of CF made it possible to be used as strain sensor. Following incorporation with PDMS, the strain sensor of CF-PDMS with high flexibility and stretchability was prepared. The sensor was sensitive to compression with compression up to 7% and extension with strain up to 50% with high durability, fast response, cyclic stability. Finally, an artificial skin based on CF-PDMS was fabricated to detect the motion of finger, demonstrating the potential applications of CF-PDMS composites in wearable electronics.

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